

CREATION AND EXPLORATION OF A PERCEPTUAL SONIC TEXTURES SPACE USING A TANGIBLE INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

This study takes place in the framework of an ongoing research dealing with the analysis, synthesis and gestural control of sonic textures. Sonic textures include a wide range of sounds featured by random properties in a short-term scale and constant characteristics in a long-term scale. In this paper, we describe two recent contributions related to this field: the first one aimed at providing a sonic textures space based on human perception. For that purpose, we conducted a psychoacoustic experiment, relying on a tangible interface, where subjects were asked to evaluate similarity between sonic textures by gathering them in several groups. The second part of this study aimed at experimenting the control of sonic textures synthesis using a tangible interactive table. We also designed a musical tabletop application inspired by the metaphor of a sonic space exploration. This gave very promising insights on the possibilities offered by such interfaces for the real-time processing of sonic textures.

1. INTRODUCTION

Before presenting the two main contributions of this paper, i.e. the creation of a perceptual space of sonic textures relying on the result of a psychoacoustic experiment and its exploration by an interactive tangible interface, we will introduce in the following sections some important concepts underlying this research: first we will bring some elements defining the class of the sonic textures, then we will compare the two approaches that can be adopted when addressing the question of sound classification and finally present the original RFID-based tangible interface we used for this study.

1.1 The sonic textures

Sonic textures are characterized in terms of both microscopic and macroscopic features: on the short-term scale, they are composed of a series of micro-structural elements which are subject to randomness, whereas on the long-term scale, the characteristics of the structure and randomness remain constant. Some environmental sounds, such as rain,

waterfalls or wind, are amongst the most obvious examples of this group of sounds but it is also possible to find textures in a musical context, especially in contemporary or electro-acoustic compositions [1]. The computer music community has recently drawn attention to sonic textures [2] and both synthesis and analysis-synthesis methods, specifically dedicated to this class of sounds, have been developed lately [3, 4].

1.2 Features-based vs. perceptual classification of sounds

Two main approaches can be followed when dealing with the characterization and classification of musical sounds. The first one refers to Music Information Retrieval (MIR) and relies on an objective description of the sound based on a series of features computed on the audio signal [5, 6]. The MIR community enhanced quickly over the last decade and a number of MIR tools, such as Marsyas¹, CLAM² or the MIRToolbox³, are hence available nowadays for experimentation.

The second strategy, which is adopted here, is a perception-based approach of sound classification. In this case, the classification does not rely on mathematical descriptors anymore but rather on the results of psychoacoustic experiments. On such experiments human listeners are asked to evaluate similarity between pairs of sounds, to gather sounds in categories or to assess distance between several groups of sounds. These methods are commonly used in studies related to instrumental timbre perception [7, 8], musical emotion assessment [9] or environmental sounds categorization [10, 11]. These two complementary approaches for sound classification, i.e. descriptors-based and perception-based, aim at addressing specific questions and provide slightly different results.

1.3 *Tangisense*, a new platform for intuitive and collaborative interaction

A tangible user interface (TUI) is a user interface in which a person interacts with digital information through the physical environment. It derives from the theoretical concept of *tangible interactivity* which states that the manipulation of real physical objects is much more efficient than the utilization of virtual widgets on a screen [12]. A part of this work is based on *Tangisense*, a platform for intuitive and collaborative interaction using an interactive table coupled

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¹ <http://www.marsyas.info>

² <http://clam-project.org>

³ <http://users.jyu.fi/~lartillo/mirtoolbox>

with tangible objects [13]. This new interface relies on RFID technology (Radio-frequency IDentification), which enables the users to manipulate tangible objects equipped with one or several RFID tags. The current prototype of Tangisense is composed of an array of 1600 RFID antennas in the form of 25 squared tiles. The surface of the interactive area is about 1m² divided in a 80x80 grid, enabling the detection of more than 60 tangible objects moving simultaneously on the table with a spatial precision of 1.25 cm. In terms of temporal resolution, the sampling rate of the table is 20 Hz, that is the position of a tangible object is refreshed every 50 ms.

Tangisense allows users to interact with two kinds of objects: '*tangible objects*', which can be found in the context of everyday life, physically accessible and easy to grasp by the user, and '*virtual objects*' displayed on the table using LED diodes associated to each RFID antenna. The original software architecture of Tangisense is written in the cross-platform language Java, but a bridge based on the OpenSoundControl protocol has been implemented to allow the table to communicate with a series of OSC-compatible programming environments such as Max/MSP, Pure Data, or Processing.

Since a couple of years touchable and tangible interfaces have been widely used for musical expression [14, 15, 16]. Due to its original RFID-based technology, Tangisense differs from most of these interfaces, which rely on computer vision tracking. One of the main advantages compared to camera-based tabletops is that Tangisense is not sensitive to lightning conditions, and does not require any preliminary calibration step before utilization. Thanks to the thickness of the tiles (15 cm), the interactive surface may be inserted in reduced spaces and placed in any position, for example vertically against a wall. The current version of this tangible table does not include multi-touch tactile display, but this functionality will be included in the next prototype, allowing direct interaction using fingers.

2. CREATION OF A PERCEPTUAL SONIC TEXTURES SPACE

In order to study the perception of sonic textures in a musical context, we conducted a psychoacoustic experiment where a series of participants were asked to gather examples of such textures in groups according to their perceived similarity. By summing up the results provided by all the participants and processing them through a multi-dimensional scaling analysis (MDS), we have been able to provide a collective map of sonic textures based on all participants' perception. This experiment was implemented in Java and used the interactive tangible table described in the previous section as control interface.

2.1 Musical sonic textures collection

For the purpose of this psychoacoustic experiment, we selected a set of 16 musical sonic textures extracted from electronic and electro-acoustic musical pieces written by

<i>Index</i>	<i>Piece</i>	<i>Composer</i>
1	Bohor	Y. Xenakis
2	Concret PH	Y. Xenakis
3	Cross Over	K. Hofstetter
4	Ermine	M. Namblard
5	Ermine	M. Namblard
6	Etheraction	J-M. Couturier
7	Foley Room	A. Tobin
8	Gobi the Desert	Monolake
9	Sur la plage à l'aube	M. Redolfi
10	La légende du jaguar	M. Redolfi
11	Microsound	C. Roads
12	Microsound	C. Roads
13	Nodal	H. Vaggione
14	Orient-Occident	Y. Xenakis
15	Tune of Wind	C-W. Weng
16	De Zarb à Daf	L. Ceccarelli

Table 1. List of musical excerpts used for the sonic textures grouping experiment.

various composers⁴, as listed in Table 1. To be selected, musical excerpts must fulfill the main criteria defining the sonic textures, i.e. presenting both short-term random properties and constant long-term characteristics. They should also present a certain degree of abstractness, i.e. the source of the sound should not be easily identifiable, in order to make the listener focus on the acoustical attributes of the textures and avoid a categorization based on the recognition of the sound source. Each excerpt was extracted as an approximately 10 seconds duration stereophonic sound file. The experimenter adjusted the loudness accordingly.

2.2 Experimental protocol

In this grouping experiment, also named *free categorization task*, subjects were asked to cluster sonic textures from a stimuli set into several groups according to their perceived similarity. As illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 2, they performed this task by manipulating three different kinds of tangible items on the interactive table:

- 16 cubic '*sound objects*' numbered from 1 to 16, associated to one sonic texture of the stimuli set,
- 4 '*basket objects*', creating virtual rectangular baskets on the table,
- one '*loudspeaker object*', allowing to draw a virtual circular listening area on the table

To listen to each sonic texture from the stimuli set, the participant had to place the actual tangible sound object within the listening area drawn around the tangible loudspeaker object. The volume of the sound was mapped according to the distance with the center of the listening area, and the size of the listening area let the possibility for the

⁴ Material related to this study, like the collection of musical excerpts used for the listening tests and videos showing the experiment process, are available online: <http://www.tele.ucl.ac.be/~jjfil/SMC10.html>

Figure 1. Representation of the tangible and *virtual* objects used in the sonic textures grouping experiment.

participant to listen to several sounds simultaneously. Then the participant was invited to gather the sounds in groups according to their similarity by putting the actual tangible sound objects within relevant virtual baskets. At the beginning of the experiment three baskets were available for the subject, who could ask for a fourth basket if needed. An important instruction given by the experimenter was that subject had no obligation to place each sonic texture in a group, in order to avoid a 'garbage basket' including heterogeneous sounds. At the end of the classification, the subject could thus leave one or several sounds unclassified, if he or she thought these sounds did not share enough similar characteristics to belong to any group.

In order to make the participant feel comfortable with both the categorization task and the manipulation of the tangible interface, time was not limited and even not measured as an indicator of subject's ability. The average duration for each user to achieve the sounds gathering was approximately fifteen minutes.

Once grouping completed, each participant answered an oral questionnaire where they were first asked to evaluate both the difficulty of the sound grouping task and the utilization of the tangible interface to complete this task. Participants were then asked to explain their categorization by describing the method they adopted to gather the sounds, and by specifying the content of the baskets by associating keywords to each class of sonic textures.

2.3 MDS analysis

For each subject participating to this experiment, a sonic textures distance matrix was created based on the result the sounds gathering. The creation of this distance matrix relied on a straightforward Boolean rule: if sounds belonged to the same group, their mutual distance was set to zero, in this opposite case, their distance was set to 1. As a consequence, leftover sounds had a distance of 0 between themselves and 1 with any other sounds. Figure 3 shows an example of sonic textures classification and the resulting individual, symmetrical and binary distance matrix.

Figure 2. A subject completing the sonic textures grouping experiment using the tangible interactive table.

Figure 3. At the top, an example of sonic textures grouping, at the bottom the resulting distance matrix.

23 participants, aged from 13 to 60 and having various degrees of musical training and experience in sound processing, performed the experiment. A global distance matrix was then put together summing all the 23 individual binary matrices. With this collective matrix, we applied a multidimensional scaling analysis (MDS) in order to construct a best-fitting geometric map of the sonic textures stimuli set.

Multidimensional scaling is a set of statistical techniques widely used in information visualization to explore similarities or dissimilarities in data [17]. It takes as an input a matrix of inter-point distances, summarizing the dissimilarities measured in the input data, and creates a configuration of points. An iterative algorithm is used to optimize the relative position of the data on the map to match the dissimilarities, which can be issued from different types of measurements. Ideally, the resulting space is in two or three dimensions, and the Euclidean distances between

them reproduce the original distance matrix. This method has been widely used in earlier works related to perceptual sound classification, especially for the creation of perceptual representation of instrumental timbre [7, 8].

Figure 4 shows the 2-D and 3-D perceptual spaces of sonic textures resulting from the MDS analysis results of the 23 participants provided after the grouping experiment.

2.4 MDS evaluation

For the purpose of our study, we fed the MDS algorithm with the 16-by-16 collective sonic textures distance matrix D , corresponding to the sum of all the individual distance matrices. MDS returned an 16-by-16 configuration matrix Y , whose rows were the coordinates of the 16 reconstructed points in a 16-dimensional space; this space could be reduced by considering only the k first columns of Y , corresponding to the reconstruction of the 16 points in a k -dimensions space. In our case, the evaluation of the MDS analysis mainly consisted of determining if the reduction to a 2-D or 3-D space, easy to visualize, provided a reasonable approximation to the original distance matrix D .

A common method consists of evaluating the sorted eigenvalues of the scalar product matrix $Y*Y'$: the relative magnitudes of those eigenvalues indicate the relative contribution of the corresponding columns of Y in reproducing the original distance matrix D with the reconstructed points. If only the first two or three eigenvalues are large, then only those coordinates of the points in Y are needed to accurately reproduce D . Figure 5 displays a scree plot of the scalar product matrix $Y*Y'$ resulting of our MDS analysis, i.e. the eigenvalues of this matrix, normalized and sorted in a descending order of magnitude. We can see two large positive eigenvalues on the scree plot, which means that the configuration of points created by the MDS can be plotted in a 2D map. The four negative eigenvalues indicate that the distances on the reconstructed space are not Euclidean, that is no configuration of points can exactly reproduce the original distance matrix D issued from the sounds grouping experiment. Fortunately, these negative eigenvalues are relatively small in comparison to the largest positive ones, which indicate that the reduction to the two first columns of Y provide a fairly accurate approximation of the distance matrix D . For a detailed description of the multidimensional scaling analysis and its evaluation methods, interested reader can refer to [17].

2.5 Discussion

Over the 23 participants who performed this experiment, 65% classified the sounds set in three groups and 35% in four groups. More than 60% of the baskets contained 4 or 5 sounds in the case of the 3-groups classification and 3 or 4 sounds in the case of the 4-groups classification. The average number of isolated sounds, i.e. not gathered with any other sounds, was 1.2 in the case of the 3-groups classification and 1.375 in the case of the 4-groups classification. Eight participants did not leave out any sound.

During the step of the verbal explanation, where subjects were asked to describe the groups according to one or

Figure 5. Scree plot of the scalar product matrix $Y*Y$, showing the sorted eigenvalues, normalized by the maximal eigenvalue, as a function of the eigenvalue index.

several keywords, interesting information came up regarding the way the sonic textures were perceived by the participants and which were criteria used by the participants to make their own classification. Four main categories came out among the keywords provided by the subjects:

- keywords describing the sound source evoked by the sonic texture: *water, nature, machines, factories, etc...*
- keywords describing the emotion evoked by the sonic texture: *relaxing, unpleasant, frightening, annoying, etc...*
- keywords related to the form of the texture, somehow linked to its temporal profile: *continuous sounds, fluid sounds, grainy sounds, smooth sounds, rhythmic sounds, percussive sounds etc...*
- keywords related to the color of the texture, which may somehow related to its spectral content: *bright, metallic, etc...*

It was interesting to note that some subjects could use the same keywords to characterize groups that included different sounds.

In terms of interaction, people agreed about the value of the tangible interface for such a free categorization task, which may sometimes turn out to be unpleasant when using a traditional mouse-based user interface. Benefits offered by such interfaces for organizing, exploring and classifying data have already been proved by the computer-human interaction community [18]. In our setting, the manipulation of physical tangible objects was quick and intuitive, and the possibility offered to the user to listen to several sounds simultaneously was very helpful to validate the grouping.

Primary conclusions can be drawn from the observation of the perceptual sonic textures spaces resulting of this psychoacoustic experiment (Figure 4). First of all, it is worth

Figure 4. 2-D and 3-D sonic textures spaces resulting of the MDS analysis.

mentioning that the positions of the sounds were relatively scattered all around the space, which reflects some kind of variability between the subjects' answers. However, clusters of sounds clearly appear in the sound space, which indicate certain coherence between the subjects' answers. For instance, 83% of the participants agreed to gather textures 5 and 10 in the same basket. These two observations - variability and consistency of subjects answers - tend to indicate that the grouping of these textures was not a trivial task.

2.6 Future tracks

This paper describes an ongoing long-term research work focused on the analysis and synthesis of sonic textures. The next step of this research will aim at attempting to interpret the geometrical configuration of the sonic textures in the perceptual map issued from the MDS analysis with regard to the factors that may explain the ordering of the points along the various dimensions of the space. We are going to describe specifically each sonic texture in terms of a series of signal descriptors typically used in music information retrieval [6], including spectral descriptors (spectral centroid, spectral spread), temporal descriptors (RMS energy, zerocrossing rate) and spectro-temporal descriptors (spectral flux, roughness). Once those features will have been combined, we will try to determine if one or several of these signal descriptors can be mapped to the dimensions of the perceptual space.

One of our assumptions, inspired by Schaeffer's approach on morphological description of sound [19], is that perception of sonic textures could be based on two main attributes, i.e. the color and the form of the texture. We assume that color of a sonic texture is related to its spectral content and could be somehow characterized by its spectral features. By form, we would like to address the notion of granularity of the textures. A descriptor based on a short-term analysis of the temporal envelope evolution could enable to quantitatively estimate this attribute. Recent works proposed by [20] and introducing a hybrid model of sound relying on both concepts of sound color and density could

be an inspirational track for the following of our research.

Among the other tracks we like to address in a near future, we plan to extend the MDS analysis by treating the collective distance matrix issued from this sound grouping experiment with a hierarchical clustering algorithm. Hierarchical clustering is a way to investigate grouping in data over a variety of scales, by creating a cluster tree [21]. This could provide complementary information to the MDS analysis. Another track we would like to investigate is the creation of an individual sonic textures space, relying on results of psychoacoustic experiments of a single subject. For that, we plan to conduct another series of listening tests including the grouping experiment followed by a second dissimilarity experiment. In this second experiment, participants will be asked to refine the classification issued from the grouping experiment by numerically rating the distance between sonic textures belonging to the same group. This would allow the creation of an individual sounds distance matrix which could then be analyzed by multidimensional scaling. This experiment has already been prototyped with the tangible interface and should be conducted in the following weeks.

3. INTERACTIVE AND TANGIBLE EXPLORATION OF A SONIC TEXTURES SPACE

This second part of our research aimed at investigating how a tangible interactive table such as Tangisense could be used for a gestural interaction with sonic textures in real-time. In order to achieve this, we designed a musical tabletop application inspired by the metaphor of the exploration of a gravitational sonic textures space.

3.1 Related works

Recently, there has been a growing interest towards experimenting multi-touch and tangible devices for musical purposes. From pioneer works, such as *Audiopad* [22] or the *Reactable* [14], to the most recent ones like the *Bricktable* [16], artists and researchers have highlighted the possibilities offered by such interfaces for musical expression

and performance. Some of these studies were dealing with the use of a tabletop interface for the exploration of sonic spaces, but addressed this question according to a MIR-oriented approach aiming at facilitating the navigation in large music collections [23, 24]. This is a slightly different approach than the one adopted in this present study, described in the next section.

3.2 A gravitational sonic space

As shown in Figure 6, we considered the sonic space as a gravitational system populated by n 'sounds attractors' which exert attraction force on m 'sound actuators' depending on their relative distance. Each attractor has its own mass, represented by the radius of its surrounding circle, which is proportional to the attraction force it exerts. The sonic interaction is designed as follow: a sound, taken from the set of sonic textures used in the psychoacoustic experiment presented above, is associated to each attractor. Each actuator generates an audio track composed of the mix of the n sonic textures associated to the attractors that are present in the space. The weight of each sonic texture in the mix depends on the forces exerted by the corresponding attractors on the actuator. In order to enhance the possibilities of interaction, we added to the actuators the ability to process the sonic textures through live granulation.

This musical experiment was developed under Max-MSP, which communicated with the interactive table through OSC. The exploration of the sonic space partly relied on interpolation tools developed by [25] and on GMU, a flexible granular synthesis environment in Max/MSP [26].

3.3 Interaction with the tangible table

As shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, the exploration of the sonic textures space is performed by manipulating three kinds of tangible objects⁵:

- 6 hemispheric tangible 'sound actuators',
- 16 cubic tangible 'sound attractors',
- one 'tangible rubber',

The tangible sound actuators are used to physically navigate in the sonic space. These objects are hemispheric and equipped with five RFID tags; beside increasing the robustness of the detection, it allows to provide information related to the inclination of the object on the table. We also chose to map the sound granulation parameters, i.e. grains length and triggering, to the rotation of the actuators.

The initial idea was to limit the exploration to a fixed perceptual sonic textures space, i.e. resulting of the psychoacoustic experiment described in section 2. However in order to increase the interactivity and enhance the possibilities of expression, we chose to give the performer the ability to freely design, populate and modify the sonic space by handling the tangible objects himself. At the beginning

⁵ a video demonstrating this musical tabletop application is available online: <http://www.tele.ucl.ac.be/~jjfil/SMC10.html>

Figure 6. Representation of a sonic textures space populated by 13 sound attractors of various mass and 4 sound actuators.

of the performance, the user could choose to load the configuration of the attractors corresponding to the perceptual map issued from the psychoacoustic experiment, or to start from an empty space and populate the sonic space by placing tangible attractors on the table. Sound attractors are represented by illuminated areas on the table; to prevent a cluttering on the table and facilitate the navigation into the sonic space, attractors were persistent, which means that they would keep their position in the sonic space even if the corresponding tangible sound object was removed from the table. A tangible rubber is placed at the disposal of the performer to remove any unwanted sound attractor.

3.4 Evaluation and future tracks

This musical tabletop application constitutes the first attempt to control real-time sound processes using the RFID-based tangible interface. The mapping between gestures and sound parameters designed in this application allows the performer to interact with sonic textures through a large range of musical gestures: while a seamless navigation in the sonic space is made possible by sliding the tangible sound actuators along the table, drawing actuator trajectories through rapid gestures allows to shape the sound matter intuitively. Multilayered soundscapes can be composed

Figure 7. The three kinds of tangible objects used for exploring the sonic textures space.

by fixing the position of some actuators in specific areas of the sonic space while moving around other actuators in different regions of the table. The exploration of the sonic space by several performers is also possible (Figure 9) and demonstrates the potential of such kind of interfaces for collaborative musical improvisation. Although the sonic space browsed in the first version of this instrument was composed of sonic textures selected for the purpose of our psychoacoustic experiment, it can easily be extended to any sound source. Such interface providing intuitive interaction with sound could thus be of interest for musicians or phonographers using field recordings as a primary sound material in their compositions.

4. CONCLUSION

The study described here above included two main parts: the first one aimed at building a space of sonic textures based on human perception. For that purpose, we conducted a psychoacoustic experiment where 23 participants were asked to gather a set of musical sonic textures extracted from various electronic or electro-acoustic pieces in a few groups according to their perceived similarity. This experiment relied on a new interactive and tangible interface based on RFID technology. A multidimensional scaling analysis (MDS) was applied to the results provided by the 23 subjects who completed the sounds grouping experiment, enabling to build both 2-D and 3-D perceptual sonic textures spaces. An important track we would like to investigate in a near future is the likely correspondence between audio descriptors of the sonic textures and dimensions of a perceptual sound space. The second part of this study was performance-oriented and aimed at investigating the possibilities offered by a tangible interface for the gestural control of sonic textures. We also designed a musical tabletop application enabling to navigate in a gravitational

Figure 8. Interactive exploration of the sonic textures space using tangible sound actuators and attractors.

Figure 9. Collaborative exploration of the sonic space by two performers

sonic texture environment through a tangible interaction. The first attempts to test this application brought up some very promising insights regarding the possibilities offered by such interfaces for the real-time processing of sonic textures.

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⁶ <http://www.cost-sid.org>

⁷ <http://www.numediart.org>

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